

Entrepreneurial Training and Business Sustainability of Beneficiaries of FIIRO Technologies

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Abstract

Entrepreneurs play significant roles in the growth and development of world economies, particularly since the 19th century. They spur industry transformations, create entirely new markets, advance wealth generation, create social change and help in community development. All these aims to give better life and end poverty in all its forms and everywhere. Entrepreneurship training is a structured program that aims to equip participants with the necessary skillset and mindset for identifying and launching new business ventures. The objective of this study is to investigate entrepreneurial training as a determinant of business sustainability in Nigeria. For this purpose, 100 beneficiaries of FIIRO technologies are selected for this study bearing the following criteria in mind: must have been trained at FIIRO between 2002 and 2020; must have established an enterprise based on technology(ies) acquired at FIIRO; must have been in business for at least two years with a product in the market and must have made the list of 100 FIIRO Successful entrepreneurs. The study adopts cross sectional research design approach and purposive and convenience sampling techniques. The instrument for primary data collection is 6-point Likert Scale questionnaire. The questionnaires are self administered to the trainees. Financial measures namely profitability, sales growth and number of employees are used to measure business sustainability while entrepreneurial training factors are measured by training content, training budget, trainer's competency, entry behaviour of trainees and trainee's exit behaviour. The data collected are analysed using Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) to examine the possible effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The findings reveal that entrepreneurial training factors have significant and positive effect on business sustainability ($r = 0.522$, $R = 0.581$, $R^2 = 0.340$ $p < 0.05$ and $F = 199.751$ at $p = 0.0000$). Therefore, it is recommended that entrepreneurs should embrace training as a matter of policy. Decision makers and management consultants should consider entrepreneurial training as pivotal to enterprise growth and development to enhance business sustainability in Nigeria.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial training, Business sustainability, Trainees, Techno-entrepreneurship development training programme.

Introduction

Studies on business sustainability is critical to business or enterprise success most especially with increasing rate of business failure occasioned by Covid-19 pandemic of which many micro, small and medium enterprises are just recovering. Micro, small and medium enterprises have been recognized as engine of economic growth in developing and developed economies. They are associated with socio-economic development creating wealth and providing jobs in overblown labour markets. A large chunk of the population in Nigeria depends on the goods and services rendered by the micro, small and medium enterprises either in the food processing sector, pharmaceutical sector, agro-processing sector, garments and apparel sector, education sector and so on. As a result, MSMEs have been a source of livelihood to many in Nigeria. As such, sustainability of MSMEs is imperative and must be accorded a topmost priority.

A sustainable business could be described as a business that can sustain itself in terms of liquidity and keeps growing with optimum profits rather than maximum year in year out with a succession plan transiting from one handler to another in a sustainable manner while maintaining balance in entrepreneurial environment or ecosystem. Entrepreneurial environment in terms of dynamism, munificence and complexity could impact on the total socioeconomic values that MSMEs could create which in turn could affect their overall success and sustainability. For MSMEs, it may be difficult to talk about enterprise sustainability if an enterprise is not profitable nor have enough sales to sustain growth. An enterprise without satisfied customers nor have competitive advantage cannot equally not be sustainable.

Many factors could be responsible for business sustainability. These could include some factors like the competency of the entrepreneur, social capital of the entrepreneur, orientation of the entrepreneur, entrepreneurial self efficacy and the type of trainings received by the entrepreneur. There is no doubt that entrepreneurial training is one of the major factors that could enhance business sustainability. However, the quality of the training is very important to achieve business sustainability. Training duration, training program objectives, training contents, competency of trainers, training budget, and mode of training delivery are critical components that could be used to measure the impact of training on business sustainability. It is also important that training contents be well structured as holistic total package incorporating both the management and technical modules to ensure attainment of training goal of ensuring business sustainability. The most common contents of the management module in entrepreneurial training for MSMEs include financial management and marketing management but others that are not so common include time management, information management, leadership and planning skills as well as communication management. For MSMEs in manufacturing concerns, technical modules such as value engineering, quality control and assurance, process reengineering, and so on are very important.

It is pertinent to note that many universities in Nigeria are setting up business schools to enhance entrepreneurial training with a view to enhancing business sustainability in Nigeria. Some of these universities include: UNN Business School, Lagos Business School (Pan African University), University of Lagos Business School, University of Ibadan Business School, Unizik Business School, Unilorin Business School, Esut Business School, ABU Business School, Uniport Business School etc. Other private business schools operating in Nigeria include: Rome Business School, International School of Management, Kaduna Business School, Jos Business School, West Africa Business Schhol, Howell Business School, Concord Business School, The Executive Business School, Dangote Business School, African Business School, MSME Business School, Delta Business School, GPE Business School, and host of others.

It is also pertinent to note that some research Institutes in Nigeria are providing techno-entrepreneurship training to entrepreneurs to promote technical enterprises based on the outcomes of the research and development efforts of such research Institutes with similar goal to enhance business sustainability. Of note in this category is the Federal Institute of Industrial Research Oshodi, Lagos whose broad mandate is to conduct research and development in the area of utilization of indigenous raw materials for rapid industrialization of the national economy through the development of the small, medium and large enterprises.

This study aims to investigate the effect of entrepreneurial training on business sustainability of FIIRO technology beneficiaries with a view to being able to make appropriate recommendations and initiate policy formulations on how business sustainability of the technology beneficiaries could be enhanced.

Conceptual Framework

Entrepreneurial Training

Entrepreneurship training is defined as any educational program or educational process that develops entrepreneurial attitudes and skills. Through entrepreneurship training individuals can gain the requisite knowledge to identify business opportunities as well as gain the skill to act on the opportunities. Effective commercialization of concepts, identifying resources and managing such resources for concept commercialization would require effective entrepreneurship training. It includes instruction in chance identification, commercializing a concept, managing resources and initiating business speculation. Entrepreneurship training programmes are effective in terms of improving business knowledge and practices (Ismail, 2018).

Entrepreneurial training is all the crucial training and skills that entrepreneurs need to succeed. It includes, among others, instructions on interpersonal management skills, enterprise planning and control, leadership training and organisational behaviour. The acquired skills prepare entrepreneurs for

the challenges they face on the job. Knowledge is an indispensable asset to any organization that, when it is properly harnessed, managed and utilized, will not only bring about increased productivity but also expansion, growth, and sustained profitability to the organization. Existing and aspiring entrepreneurs have been imparted positively to promote best business practices through entrepreneurship training programmes which provide training for entrepreneurs with grants, mini finance, and mentoring interventions (McKenzie & Woodruff, 2013). The extent to which the interventions can achieve their objectives would depend on the contents, duration and intensity of the intervention programmes. It may therefore, be difficult to reach a consensus on what should constitute an effective entrepreneurship training programmes. It has been found that some entrepreneurship trainings that incorporate finance are more effective towards creating self employments as well enhancing best practices in business (Cho & Honorati, 2014; De Mel et al., 2014; Patel, 2014). Easy access to grant would likely keep many entrepreneurs in self employments to perform their traditional role of job creation (Martinez et al., 2016).

The goal of entrepreneurship training programmes is for creation of self employments through star ups but attainment of this goal can be described as modest. This is evident in Chile and Sri Lanka where self employments was found to decline after two years of entrepreneurial training interventions (De Mel et al., 2014; Martinez et al., 2016).

Some studies have also shown that effects of entrepreneurship training programmes on some measures of business performance namely profits, sales revenue, and inventory are modest. A study has revealed that entrepreneurial training has no effect on income (Cho & Honorati, 2014) whereas, little improvements in sales, income, capital stock and loan activity have been observed in some studies (De Mel et al., 2014; Field, Jayachandran, & Pande, 2010; Karlan & Valdivia, 2011; Martinez et al., 2016).

It has been observed that entrepreneurship training programmes are very effective when it comes to enhancing business knowledge and ensuring good business practices (De Mel, McKenzie, & Woodruff, 2014; Patel, 2014). For instance, in a meta-analysis of thirty seven training programmes, the training programmes have positive effects on business practices among existing small businesses (Cho & Honorati, 2014) whereas results from some studies noted improvements record-keeping, asset management and recognition of the enterprise as a legal entity (Giné & Mansuri, 2014; Martinez et al., 2016). Such improvements have been reported to have long term sustainability (De Mel et al., 2014).

Some entrepreneurship studies with focus on entrepreneurship training for women entrepreneurs have imparted positively on their business performance with a specific finding that sound knowledge of business planning acquired during entrepreneurship training is useful for them in goal and target setting for their enterprises (Bauer, 2011; Patel, 2014). Patel (2014) also reported that entrepreneurship training is of benefit for female entrepreneurs through confidence building and self empowerment (Patel, 2014) though some cultural and religion barriers to women's involvement in business activities still hinder full participation of women in business (Field et al., 2010; Giné &

Mansuri, 2014). For instance, in India and Pakistan, restrictions to movement of women is undermining the entrepreneurial activities of women though encouragement of women-to-women business in social networks is gradually improving women participation in entrepreneurial activities (Patel, 2014).

Entrepreneurship training programmes have an overall statistically significant and positive impact on business practices (0.075). Existing business owners (0.084) derive greater benefits from the training than potential entrepreneurs. (Patel 2015) finds that entrepreneurship training improves business knowledge of female entrepreneurs. A qualitative assessment of two training programmes in Vermont, USA (Women's Small Business Programme and the Microbusiness Development Programme) for women entrepreneurs found that learning how to build a business plan was regarded as a key benefit of the programme by the participants (Bauer, 2011). It is, therefore, paramount to understand that entrepreneurship training programme is a major driver of entrepreneurship development and therefore a major force in the economic growth particularly of developing nations; it is an agent of job creation and it enhances competitiveness (Waita, 2014).

Business development has received a great boost from Entrepreneur Development Training Programmes (EDTPs) which operate on the assumption that through appropriate entrepreneurial training, more individuals would start entrepreneurial ventures. These trainings are well structured to deliver skills capable of attitudinal change in individuals towards motivating them to become prospective entrepreneurs (Park & Choi, 2018).

In summary, from all the definitions and descriptions of entrepreneurship training, the main goal of entrepreneurship training appears to be the same with the different authors. This goal is to enhance business performance or success through impartation of appropriate skills, competencies (management and technical), in a training program designed with appropriate training contents, training budget and trainers with appropriate competency.

Business Sustainability

The term sustainable development was introduced by the United Nations with the notion that for economic development to be sustainable it must meet the needs of the present with no compromise for the needs of the future generation.

How to Act on Sustainable Business

Source: T. Bansal, 2022

With this background, we can describe a sustainable business as that business that is able to create wealth and enhances people's lives with no compromise for the wealth and wellbeing of the future generation. Businesses must be planned in a way that natural resources which are factors of production are not depleted too quickly with no control but such must be of necessity extracted or exploited in a controlled manner to balance the ecosystems.

Sustainable development is illustrated in the diagram above on how to handle issue of sustainability within an organization, with other organizations and with the society.

- i. In one's organization, sustainability should begin at home by getting one's house in order.
- ii. With other organizations, the impact of one's sustainability efforts can be increased through working with other organizations.
- iii. With society, collaboration with other parts of the society such as local communities, none governmental organization etc is required to address sustainability issues.

Entrepreneurship development is one of the most effective tools for enhancing poverty reduction and eradication, as well as achieving sustainable development (Adejuwon & Adeigbe, 2018). Business sustainability has been conceptualized as gaining financial returns from entrepreneurial actions with good growth rates or indices or good performance in stock market (Davidsson & Honig, 2003) as well as showing good indices on non financial performance such as satisfaction of employees, fulfilment and satisfaction of the business owners/entrepreneurs through personal achievements (Kakabadse, 2015). In the definition of entrepreneurial sustainability, offered by Limsong, Sambath, Sean & Hong (2016), entrepreneurial sustainability is defined to gains from financial and non financial entrepreneurial activities of the entrepreneur.

It has been documented that most businesses closed their shops after one year in operation and only 5 to 10% of businesses survive the first five years in operation (Makarenko, Chernysheva Polyakova & Makarenko, 2019). Some authors have conducted empirical research on why some businesses are not successful, and therefore not sustainable, and have identified the following as some of the reasons: leadership skills challenge, competitor's activities, differences in expectation, and economic crises (Miettinen & Littunen, 2013; Sakiru et. al, 2013). These factors need to be integrated into entrepreneurship training programmes.

Strategies used by small coffee owners in Duval County, Florida, USA to achieve success in business beyond five years have been investigated. Three major strategies were identified namely: networking by the business owners through positioning the business on their websites as venues for customers to meet and network; managing the business with the enterprise business plan as blueprint by assessing milestones, addressing challenges and changes from time to time; and deploying marketing differentiation strategy (Turner & Endres, 2017). Empirical evidence has shown that the personality of the entrepreneur is a critical factor for business success and sustainability, having observed that while operating under the same conditions, some entrepreneurs were able to manage their businesses to success whereas others cannot but go bankrupt (Kambey, Wuryaningrat, & Kumajas, 2018; Sycheva, et. al., 2018).

Krock & Anderson (2016) identified business processes optimization and automation, as well as employee's training as success factors in McDonald business. Confidence, ability to make decisions with ease and social communication skills have also been identified as business success and sustainability factors (Shepelenko & Chernysheva, 2018). Makarenko et. al., (2019) concluded in their study on business success factors that the following are important success factors for businesses: deep knowledge of business; clear definition of business goal(s); innovative ideas in operating the business; transparency; competent and motivated staff and realism in business.

Business success and sustainability can be measured by both financial and non-financial factors. Umoren & Udofot (2014) measured business success with success factors outside the domain of finance using employee's composition, entrepreneurial motivation and strategy implementation as success indicators. Entrepreneurial factors, and business environment factors were used to measure entrepreneurial success in a study carried out in the UK chemical distribution industry (Lampadarios, 2017). The characteristics of the entrepreneurs, external business environment and government's supportive factors have been reported to have positive relationship with business success or performance of women businesses in Pakistan, with internal business environment having little significance impact on success. Though perceived national culture has no influence on the success of women owned businesses, it was found to weaken the positive relationship existing between entrepreneur's characteristics and performance; however, it enhances the impact of supportive factor measures on performance (Shakeel, Yaokuang & Gohar, 2020).

Internal environment variable with business innovation, development of strategy and record maintenance as success measures and external environment variable with external knowledge source, appropriate market, available opportunities and technological advantages as measures have been reported (Al-Tit, Omri & Euch, 2019); Gonzalez-Rodriguez, Jimenezcaballero, Martinsamper, Koseoglu, & Okumus, 2018; Long, Looijen, & Blok, 2018) Other researchers have studied the impact of individual characteristics on business success using entrepreneurial trait, education, managerial skills, motivation as success measures (Gupta & Mirchandani, 2018; Welsh, Kaciak, & Shamah, 2018). The factors identified as impacting or affecting successful and sustainable entrepreneurship are embedded in promoting sustainable entrepreneurship training.

Promoting Sustainable Entrepreneurship in Training and Education

Sustainability emerged from sustainable development, meaning development that meets the need of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (WCED, 1987) In Binder et al., 2015 as cited by Zahrani, 2022, five components that are normally part of definitions of sustainability entrepreneurship are highlighted. The first is the interest of academics in the process that lead to how possibilities are identified, developed and exploited. The second is the reinforcement of the notion that sustainable development must provide a balance in the link inherent in economic, social, and ecological effects of entrepreneurial activities. Thirdly, the potential for transformation of future products and services form part of the definitions. The fourth component that should be reflected in the definition of entrepreneurial sustainability is the incorporation of the source of opportunities and how they are generated by resourceful entrepreneurs including through market weakness and how to take advantage of such weakness. Finally, the definition should of necessity include who takes advantage of chances or the opportunities and in this case, it is the entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurial process has been the main focus of many entrepreneurship studies in the area of sustainable entrepreneurship research (Belz & Binder, 2017).

Social entrepreneurship and innovation have been observed to have positive impact on creation of values and to sustain economic development (Wang, 2022). Sometimes, sustainable entrepreneurial process is initiated by noneconomic advantages and emotions. In such case, the experience is that the shared vision between the founders, the firm and the firm's members is developed by the compassion to promote the well-being of others (Farny, 2016). Sustainable entrepreneurship process begins with identifying a specific ecological or social problem (Belz & Binder, 2017). Then, it is very important that entrepreneurs must possess the necessary skills and incentive sufficient enough for community improvement or social well-being in order to be sustainable (Muñoz & Cohen, 2018).

Instructors or trainers in sustainable entrepreneurship focus their teachings on how entrepreneurs will use current resources sustainably for the success of their enterprises without risking the ability of future generations to access resources (Hermes & Rimanoczy, 2018). "Preservation of nature, intensive care,

and society in order to pursue perception opportunity to bring into presence products in the future, processes, and services for benefit, where gain is broadly construed to include financial and non-gains to individuals, the economy, and society,” (Shepherd & Patzelt, 2011) define sustainable entrepreneurship. In the definition, it is important to note that sustainable entrepreneurship is not just about enterprise creation of sustainable enterprises but also includes management and transformation of existing businesses towards making them more sustainable. This confirms that sustainable entrepreneurship is a concept for all levels of enterprises including start-ups, micro, small, medium and large enterprises (Gast et al., 2017). Given its significance, state that the goal of sustainable entrepreneurship is to build a more sustainable and equitable society.

Several institutions throughout the globe have launched research and training programs on sustainable entrepreneurship in order to play a vital role in the development of sustainable societies (Décamps et al., 2017; Olalla & Merino, 2019). To give sustainable entrepreneurship education modules, educators frequently combine sustainability-related themes with entrepreneurship education (Gast et al., 2017). In general, sustainable entrepreneurial education and training aims to assist existing, emerging, and potential entrepreneurs in new relationship development that would be of help in confronting future challenges and responsibilities aside from increasing their skills (Chandra, 2016). This is one of the objectives of the FIIRO entrepreneurship training programme.

Sustainable entrepreneurship is derived from crossbreeding of sustainable development and entrepreneurship. Since the introduction of the concept of sustainable development by UN, sustainable development and its implication for human development has been a major topic of discourse amongst policy makers, academia, industry and the society at large. It is most generally characterized as “filling current demands without jeopardizing future generations' capacity to fulfil their own needs” (World Commission on Environment and Development, 1987). Sustainable development acknowledges the interrelationship between natural environment, welfare of the society, economic performance and sustainable entrepreneurship but in this, sustainable development must aim to preserve intra-generational equity while at the same time developing inter-generational equity.

In summary, the concept of entrepreneurial sustainability is a very wide and it is a very important concept that ensures business survival in sustainable manner. Authors have agreed that entrepreneurial sustainability involves commercializing an identified business opportunity, and the exploitation of the commercialized business opportunity in a way that create wealth for the entrepreneur without compromising the wellbeing and the wealth of future generations such that economy, social and ecology operate on a balance tripod for the betterment of the society.

Theoretical Framework

This study is based on two relevant theories, the success factor theory and human capital theory.

Success Factor Theory

Success factor as a concept was first used in management literature by Ronald Daniel (1961). He posited that success factors are the same for all companies operating within the same industry. Rockart (1979) was of the opinion that success factors are very critical to business success and sustainability. Khandelwal and Ferguson (1999) observed that success factor approach was initially not fully developed and limited in application, but today, the approach is applicable in all areas of management study. With this observation, Wronka (2013) and Manoj, Kumar, Van Goubergen, Molnar, & Gellynck (2013) reported that success factors can find fundamental usage in every kind of ventures. Gierszewska & Romanwaska (2007) described success factors as tools for analysis to evaluate the image of an industry. Causal-effect relationship was studied by Perato. In his study, he observed that 80% of effects are obtained from 20% of the causes. Wronka (2013) reported that the main aim of the success factor theory is for the organization that desire success to concentrate organizational efforts on the 20% of the causes that is producing 80% of the success for the organization. In success factor theory, organization must identify the limited areas that will ensure organizational success. However, if these factors are not managed well, organizational failure is inevitable (Moohebat, Asemi, & Jazi, 2010.). Management process and decision making is usually complex as a result of many factors. With success factors theory, these complexities could be minimized through concentrating effort on the most critical success factors (Alzahrani & Emsley, 2013; Bai & Sarkis, 2013).

Entrepreneurship needs to understand and make use of the success factor to be able to remain sustainable. This study therefore, finds relevance in success theory because the goal of every entrepreneurial activity is success and no enterprise can be sustainable without being a success in the first instance.

Human Capital Theory

Human capital theory has been described by Bohlander, Snell, & Sherman (2001) to include some kind of skills, knowledge and capabilities acquired by individuals through formal school system or through training on the job to create economic value for an organization. Dess and Pickens (1999) viewed human capital from personal traits point of view which is peculiar to an individual and cannot be separated from an individual possessing them and such include individual capabilities, skills, knowledge and experience capable of adding value to an organization to ensure entrepreneurial success and sustainability. Human capital theory draws its relevance in its application targeted at increasing organizational performance through the skills, knowledge, ability and experience of employees. Introduction of the term human capital into academic arena was by Theodore W. Schultz (1961) as published in the American Economic Review. Human capital theorist believes higher level of education and training will contribute higher input in terms of skills, knowledge and ability to organizational goals (Blair, 2012).

Gary Backer (1964) defined human capital as a physical means of production while Becker (1964) posited that human capital can be accumulated in different forms of education, training, migration, and health. Human capital theory also viewed employees as assets which must be well developed and properly integrated in an organization for efficient and effective performance (Vejchayanon, 2005). To the resources-based theorists, the human capital of an entrepreneurs consists of both management skills and tacit knowledge (Lerner & Almor, 2002), previous entrepreneurial experience, and family background (Dzisi, 2008). The human capital theory, with emphasis on human capital development embracing individual capabilities, skills, knowledge, and experience capable of adding value to an organization to ensure entrepreneurial success and sustainability, makes the theory very relevant for this study.

In this study, entrepreneurship training is expected to bring about business sustainability. Therefore, this study also finds relevance in human capital theory with assertion that the skills or the training an individual acquired could create economic value for an organization. In this case, economic value attained through entrepreneurship training could bring about business sustainability.

Empirical Review

The relationship between entrepreneurship training and entrepreneurial orientation was investigated using a quasi-experimental approach of the sharp regression discontinuity design to test the relationship with a sample of 1330 micro enterprises. The results show a positive and significant causal relationship between entrepreneurship training and all three dimensions of entrepreneurial orientation (Al-Awlaqi, Ammar & Habtoor, 2018).

The relationship between entrepreneurship education (EE) and the core values of sustainable development (CVSD) has been investigated under the condition of entrepreneurial skill developed by undergraduates (ESDU) as a mediator variable (Edokpolo, 2020). A structured questionnaire was used in this correlational study to obtain responses from 399 Nigerian university undergraduates purposively selected for the study. The results indicate that entrepreneurial skills developed by undergraduates (ESDU) has a positive and statistically significant mediating effect on the entrepreneurship education (EE)-core values of sustainable development relationship (CVSD) (Edokpolo, 2020).

In a study on the role of entrepreneurship training on the growth of micro and small enterprises, entrepreneurship training was measured by training objective, training content, trainer's competency and training delivery methods, the result of descriptive and thematic analysis show that entrepreneurship training components contribute to certain extent towards business growth of the micro and small enterprise in Kiambu County (Mukulu & Marima, 2017).

Effect of entrepreneurship training on sustainability of SMEs in Morogoro Municipa Council, Tanzania was studied with 62 respondents selected using convenience and purposive sampling techniques with questionnaire as research instrument. The data collected was analysed using IBM SPSS

Version 20. The results show that entrepreneurship training has a positive and significant relationship effect on business sustainability (Iganile, 2019).

Orobia (2020) carried out an empirical study on entrepreneurial framework conditions and business sustainability amongst youths and women entrepreneurs. In this study, entrepreneurial framework is measured by entrepreneurial training/education, government program and policies, IT infrastructure, market openness, and finance while business sustainability is measured by stakeholders' engagement, people and skills, ecosystem management, market and sales and innovation. Correlation results show that all the five measures of entrepreneurial framework conditions including entrepreneurial training/education have positive and significant association with individual measures of business sustainability Regression analysis however, show that only finance and IT infrastructure have positive and significant impact on business sustainability among the youth and women.

In a study to investigate the effect of entrepreneurial training, skills and networking on youth business sustainability, 150 participants drawn from five batches of entrepreneurship training programs organised and sponsored by government agencies, the results show that entrepreneurial training, skills and networking have positive and significant effect on business sustainability resulting in business continuity among youths (Manaf, Misnan, Wallang & Dollah, 2020).

Strategic entrepreneurship has been investigated as a predictor of business sustainability in a study conducted with 237 participants from 3 textile companies in Lagos State using questionnaire to collect responses from all the respondents. Process analysis of regression results show that strategic entrepreneurship has significant positive effect on business sustainability of the companies under study. When the relationship was studied under the condition of level of education as a moderator, level of education has a negative and insignificant moderating effect on the strategic entrepreneurship – business sustainability relationship (Tijani, Egwuonwu and Akinlabi, 2020).

Cho & Honorati (2014) in a qualitative study to examine the effects of training and development packages on the success of women small scale business owners in Ghana most especially women mostly single mothers who are operating at Dansoman Market in the Metropolitan Accra Region. The results show that most of the women traders who have no training whatsoever in financial, marketing nor human resource management are doing badly in their businesses while those with training are doing well in their businesses. On the impact of training duration on the success of the training programme, a u-shaped relationship was found between the duration of training and the likelihood of success of the programme with implication that short and intense training is more effective than training that is extended over a long period (Cho & Honorati, 2014).

McKenzie & Woodruff (2013) undertake a critical review of previous studies in entrepreneurial training with the goal of synthesizing the emerging lessons and understanding the limitations of the existing research and the areas in which more work is needed. It was found out that there is substantial heterogeneity in the length, content, and types of firms participating in the training programs evaluated.

It was discovered that many of the evaluations were done with low level of statistics with impact of training measure within one year of training which may not be sufficient enough for generalization. Other issues observed in the studies are survey attrition and measurement of firm profits and revenues. It was observed in literature that training made modest impacts on some surviving firms but stronger evidence abound that training programs assists prospective owners to launch new businesses faster. Though, majority of the studies indicated that business owners implemented some of the skills learnt during trainings but such skills couldn't make much impact on business performance. However, some few studies shows that training has significant impacts on profits or sales while others found benefits to microfinance organizations of offering training. It is difficult to conclude in literature whether positive impact found on business performance was actually as a result of training acquired by entrepreneurs or some other factors influencing business performance.

Vuuren, & Botha (2010) applied the constructs of the entrepreneurial performance training model to three different training interventions, known as the business start-up, basic entrepreneurship, and advanced entrepreneurship programmes. Furthermore, the paper measured the business performance indicators and skills transfer that took place after the training interventions. Quantitative research was conducted, using three validated quantitative research questionnaires. The research design consists of a pre-test, post-test and post-post test (ten weeks after the training interventions took place). Factor analysis was done, descriptive statistics arising from opinions and expressions are presented and statistical tests such as the Chi Square test and ANOVA provide inferential statistics. It was found out that the business performance indicators improved for all three training groups after they attended the training interventions. Furthermore, it was proved that skills transfer took place after the respondents attended the training interventions.

In summary, most studies in literature confirmed that entrepreneurship training has significant positive effect on business sustainability. Main components or measures of entrepreneurship training include training objective, training duration, training budget, competency of trainers, and training delivery methods while business sustainability is measured by stakeholders' engagement, people and skills, ecosystem management, market and sales and innovation.

Hypothesis and Significance of the Study

The hypothesis of the study is that entrepreneurial training will have no significant effect of business sustainability of FIIRO technologies beneficiaries (H_0). The study uses beneficiaries of FIIRO technologies who have established their own enterprises based on technologies acquired at FIIRO.

The study is significant in the following ways: to increase indigenous knowledge on determinants of business sustainability; to improve management consultancy practices for entrepreneurship by providing management consultants with useful information needed to develop training programmes to enhance business sustainability; to enhance industrial development through

appropriate policy formulation for entrepreneurship development at all levels of government- federal, state and local; personal development for individual entrepreneurs to enhance performance and finally, to aid research students in various areas, particularly in entrepreneurial studies and business sustainability, by serving as a reference point for subsequent researches.

Scope of the Study

The study covers entrepreneurs who are beneficiaries of FIIRO technologies through the Institute's techno-entrepreneurship training and technology transfer training programmes and have established enterprises based on the technologies acquired. This study also covered technology beneficiaries who were trained at FIIRO between 2002 and 2020 who have established enterprises based on the technologies acquired at FIIRO.

Methodology

Cross-sectional research design is adopted on this study. The study population is the trainees at the techno-entrepreneurial development training programme at FIIRO. Purposive and convenience sampling techniques are used to select 100 samples for the study from 250 beneficiaries of FIIRO technologies. The 100 samples selected for this study are the beneficiaries of FIIRO technologies who have been in business continuously for minimum of two years; who have at least one product in the market and has made the list of "100 Successful FIIRO Entrepreneurs". The instrument for primary data collection is 6-point Likert Scale questionnaire. The questionnaire is divided into three sections. The first section is on demographics of the respondents. The second section is designed to solicit responses on entrepreneurial training factors while the third section is designed to solicit responses from the respondents on business sustainability dimensions. The questionnaire was self administered to the trainees during training sessions. The response rate is 100%. Business sustainability is measured by financial indicators namely profitability, sales growth and number of employees; while entrepreneurial training is measured by training contents, training budget, trainer's competency, training duration, trainee's entry behaviour and trainees exit behaviour. These training components are to ensure effective and efficient training for business sustainability. The data collected was analyzed using Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) to examine the possible effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable.

Findings

On gender of the respondents, the result reveals that 67% of respondents were males while 33% were females. This means that more males participated in the study than the female counterparts. 16% of the respondents were between the age range of 21-30 years, 27% were between 31-40 years, 29% were between 41- 50 years, while 28% were between 51 years and above. This means that respondents, whose

age fall between 41-50 years were in the majority and respondents whose fall between 21-30 years (16%) were the minority. This implies that 57% of the respondents are adults. The highest number of respondents are married (68%) while 7% are divorcees. 16% are single and 9% were not willing to disclose their marital status. On educational qualifications of the respondents, 57% of the respondents have first degree or its equivalent while 24% are Masters degree holders, 11% have National Diploma/National Certificate in Education while 8% has PhD degrees. This implies that first degree holders participated more in the study while the least that participated in term of educational level are the PhD holders. On number of years in business, 46% of the respondents indicated they have been in business between 6-10 years while 29% indicated they have been in business between 11 – 15 years. 16% of the respondents have been in business between 1 – 5 years while 9% of the respondents have been in business between 16-20 years. This implies that most of the respondents (46%) have been in business between 6-10 years whereas only 9% have been in business for over 16 years.

Test of Hypothesis

H₀: Entrepreneurial training will have no significant effect on business sustainability of FIIRO technologies beneficiaries.

Table 1 a-c: Regression Analysis

Model Summary				
Model	R	R ²	Adjusted square	Std Error of the Estimate
1	.5814 ^a	.340	.339	.53783

^a Predictor: Constant Entrepreneurial

Training

Source: Field Survey, (2022)

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	57.938	1	57.938	199.751	.000 ^b
	Residual	112.231	388	.289		
	Total	170.169	389			

^aDependent variable: Business Sustainability

^bPredictor: (Constant) Entrepreneurial Training

Source: Field Survey Results (2022)

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardised Coefficient	Standardised Coefficient	T	Sig.
1	Constant	B	Std Error	Beta	
	Entrepreneurial Training	2.373	.189		12.567 ‘000
		.520	.037	.534	14.153 ‘000

^aDependent Variable: Entrepreneurial Training

Table 1a-c shows the findings of the regression analysis for the effect of entrepreneurial training on business sustainability.

Table 1a gives a model summary which indicates how the model equation fits into the data. The R^2 was used to establish the predictive power of the study's model. From the findings, entrepreneurial training has modest and significant link with entrepreneurial sustainability ($R = 0.581, p < 0.05$)

The coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.330 demonstrates that entrepreneurial training explained 34 percent of the variance in business sustainability whereas the remaining 67% variation in business sustainability is explained by other exogenous variable distinct from those investigated in this research. This result suggests that entrepreneurial training influence 34% of business sustainability. It is vital to underline that the impact projected by entrepreneurial training is favourable yet modest.

Table 1b presents the results of ANOVA (overall model significance) of regression test which revealed that entrepreneurial training has a significant influence on business sustainability. This can be explained by the F value (199.751) at $p = 0.000$ which is statistically significant at 95% confidence interval. Furthermore, the results of regression coefficients in table 1c revealed that at 95% confidence level, a unit change in entrepreneurial training will lead to a 0.520 increase in business sustainability given that all other factors are held constant. On the strength of this finding [$R^2 = 0.330, F (199.751, p = 0.000)$], this research rejects the null hypothesis which states that entrepreneurial training has no significant effect on business sustainability.

Discussion of Findings

Results from the test of hypothesis show that there is significant positive relationship between entrepreneurial training and business sustainability. The findings show that an increase in entrepreneurial training will have a positive and significant influence on business sustainability. The outcome of linear regression study for the effect of entrepreneurial training on business sustainability reveals that entrepreneurial training has a major effect on business sustainability. The findings revealed that entrepreneurial training factors have significant and positive effect on business sustainability ($r = 0.522, R = 0.581, R^2 = 0.340, p < 0.05$ and $F = 199.751$ at $p = 0.0000$).

The findings are in line with the findings reported by Manaf, Misnan, Wallang & Dollah, (2020) which conclude that entrepreneurship training has a positive and significant effect on business sustainability. Also, the results agree with the result reported Iganile (2019) on the study on the effect of entrepreneurship training on sustainability of SMEs in Morogoro Municipal Council, Tanzania entrepreneurship training was found to have a positive and significant effect on business sustainability. Orobia (2020), in an empirical study on entrepreneurial framework conditions and business sustainability amongst youths and women entrepreneurs reported a correlation result showing that all the five measures of entrepreneurial framework conditions including entrepreneurial training/education have positive and significant association with individual measures of business sustainability which is in alignment with the findings of this study. Also, in agreement with the results of this study is the result of a correlational study by Edokpolo (2020) which confirms that entrepreneurship education has a positive and significant effect on business sustainability while entrepreneurial skills was reported to have a positive and statistically significant mediating effect on the entrepreneurship education-business sustainability relationship.

Fifty seven percent of the respondents in this study have higher education which could probably explain the strength of entrepreneurial training-business sustainability observed in this study. The observation is in agreement with the study reported by Hunady, Orviska & Pizar (2018) and Blair (2012) whose results suggest that higher education is beneficial to new business and a strong factor that determines the success and sustainability of new enterprises.

Gender could be said to play a role in the study's outcomes noting that 67% of the respondents are male. Some researchers have reported that many men start businesses and run them successfully because many push and pull factors made them to do so and they tend to engage more in malpractices that could aid business growth than women counterparts (Hazudin, Kader, Tarmuji, Ishak, & Ali, R, 2015). Age of the respondents appears to influence the outcome of the study with observation that 57% of the respondents are adults who are above 40 years in age. On the number of years in business, 84% of respondents have been in business for over 5 years. Successful and sustainable business has been described to include a business that has been in existence for over five years (Turner & Endres, 2017). Also, the finding of the study agrees with the findings of Islam, Khan, Odaidullah & Alam (2011) who reported that entrepreneurs that operated longer period have been more successful than those who have been in operation for a shorter period. On marital status, the highest number of the respondent (68%) is married. This appears to have influence on the outcome of this study, in agreement with the findings of Dada & Fayomi (2015) who reported significant correlation between marriage and business performance.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study provides an empirical insight on the links between entrepreneurial training and business sustainability of the beneficiaries of FIIRO technologies, Lagos, Nigeria for a period of 2002 and 2020.

The problem of insufficient and inappropriate entrepreneurial training has been one of the major challenges impeding business sustainability in Nigeria. The study formulated a main objective, develop hypothesis and evaluated the responses of the respondents using appropriate statistical methods. The results reveal that entrepreneurial training factors have significant and positive effect on business sustainability.

Based on the outcome of this study, it is recommended that government and other agencies with responsibilities to develop entrepreneurship in Nigeria should consider the findings of this study in developing and implementing appropriate policies for entrepreneurship development in Nigeria. Management consultants with specialization in entrepreneurship development should also consider the findings of the study when designing training programmes to enhance entrepreneurial operations and business sustainability.

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